
**Molecular Basis of Cell Cycle Arrest by Erufosine in Breast and
Colorectal Cancer Cell Lines**

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By

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CERTIFICATE

It is hereby certified that thesis is based on the results of the experiments carried out by Muhammad Shoaib Akhtar and that it has not been previously presented for M.Phil. degree. Mr. Muhammad Shoaib Akhtar has done this research work under my supervision. He has fulfilled all the requirements and qualified to submit the accompanying thesis for the degree of M.Phil. Medical Laboratory Sciences in Molecular Pathology and Cytogenetics.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Akt	Protein Kinase B
ALPs	Alkylphospholipids
ASR	Age Standardized Rates
CDK	Cyclin Dependant Kinases
cDNA	Complimentary Deoxyribonucleic Acid
CRC	Colorectal Cancer
DISC	Death Inducing Signalling Complex
DKFZ	German Cancer Research Centre
DNA	Deoxyribonucleic Acid
<i>E.</i>	Epidermophyton
ER	Estrogen
ErPC	Erucylphosphocholine
ErPC3	Erufosine
FNAC	Fine Needle Aspiration Cytology
FOBT	Faecal Occult Blood Test
HER2	Human Epidermal Growth Factor 2
INMOL	Institute of Nuclear Medicine and Oncology, Lahore
IPA	Ingenuity Pathways Analysis Software
KCR	Karachi Cancer Registry
KIRAN	Karachi Institute of Radiotherapy and Nuclear Medicine
LysoPC	Lysophosphatidylcholines
MTD	Maximum Tolerated Dose
MTT	3-[4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2,5 diphenyltetrazolium bromide

NCBI	National Centre for Biotechnology Information
PCR	Polymerase Chain Reaction
PKC	Protein Kinase C
qRT-PCR	Quantitative Real-time Polymerase Chain Reaction
RNA	Ribonucleic Acid
<i>Spp.</i>	Species
<i>T₁</i>	Trypanosoma
<i>T₂</i>	Trichophyton
TNM	Tumour-Necrosis-Metastasis

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ABSTRACT

Background: Breast and colorectal cancers are the leading causes of cancer related mortalities worldwide. Treatment options are limited for advanced stages of these cancers. In this context, search for more effective therapeutic compounds is inevitable. Erufosine, a synthetic 4th generation alkyl-phosphocholine, has shown its anticancer potential over the last few years against a variety of cell lines belonging to solid and non-solid cancers. The reported toxic effects were found to be highly tumour cell specific with minimal side-effects including reduced haemolytic activity and less harmful nature for bone marrow.

Aim: Purpose of this study was to evaluate molecular basis of the cytostatic effects imposed by erufosine in breast and colorectal cancers.

Materials & Methods: In preliminary phase, toxic effects of erufosine were identified against breast (MDA-MB-231, MCF-7) and colorectal cancer cell lines (SW480, SW620) by MTT proliferation assays. Afterwards, the cells were exposed to erufosine and cytostatic effects were evaluated by propidium iodide based staining and flow-cytometry. In this study, metastatic breast (MDA-MB-231) and colorectal (SW620) cancer cell lines were treated with erufosine and expressional modulations in 84 cell cycle relevant genes were identified by using a ready-made 96-well panel and qRT-PCR methodology. Expressional changes, imposed by erufosine in the cell lines, were used to design a signalling cascade with the help of online *Ingenuity Pathway Analysis* software. Afterwards, breast (MDA-MB-231, MCF-7) and colorectal cancer (SW480, SW620) cells were treated with various concentrations of erufosine and expressional levels of the three most altered genes, selected from the ready-made panel results, were investigated to identify concentration dependant effects of the test compound.

Results: Preliminary results indicated that erufosine induced significant anti-proliferative effects in breast and colorectal cancer cells. In addition, erufosine was found to be a strong cytostatic agent and induced a major halt in G2/M phase of the cell cycle in breast and colorectal cancer cells. Ready-made panel results showed significant modulations (≥ 2 fold) in various cell cycle related genes after exposure of the cells with erufosine. The designed pathway indicated the involvement of a number of gene families at different stages of the cell cycle. Exposure of the cells with various concentrations of erufosine showed concentration dependant effects of the compound on expressional profile of the selected genes.

Conclusion: Erufosine bears significant cytotoxic and cytostatic potential against breast and colorectal cancer cells. Expressional modulations in multiple cell cycle related genes are imposed by erufosine in breast and colorectal cancer cells. Further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies are required to support the evaluation of erufosine in clinical settings against breast and colorectal cancer.

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Breast Cancer

Breast cancer is a disease that develops from malignant cells formation in breast tissue. Breast is a mammary gland made up of lobules that make and carry milk. Breast tissue also contains fat, lymph nodes, and blood vessels. The most common type of breast cancer is ductal carcinoma. Other breast cancer types include ductal carcinoma in situ, invasive breast cancer and inflammatory breast cancer (Stewart and Wild, 2017).

A variety of risk factors contribute to breast cancer in addition to being female: incidence of breast cancer increases with every 10 years of life till menopause (after menopause incidence decreases slowly); women menstruating early and women with late menopause are also at increased risk; women with first pregnancy after 30 years of age are two times at more risk than women with first pregnancy before 20 years of age; it also inherits as autosomal dominant condition in 10% women in western countries; benign breast disease increases four to five times higher risk; ionising radiations may increase risk of carcinogenesis; obesity increases two times more risk of breast cancer in postmenopausal women; women with oral contraceptives are slightly at increased risk while diet, smoking, and alcohol consumption do not have any consistent risk (McPherson et al., 2000).

Symptoms of breast cancer include breast lump, variation in breast shape, skin dimpling at breast, an uncontrolled fluid from nipple and red scaly patch of skin (Watson, 2008, Society, 2007).

Diagnosis of breast cancer depends upon training and perception of general physician. Women usually self-report to their physician about their breast lump. Physical

examination with mammography is sufficient to make a diagnosis of breast cancer but lump cytology using FNAC or excision biopsy may be needed sometimes. Ultrasound, CT scan and MRI also provide support for establishing diagnosis (Society, 2007, Watson, 2008, Kabel and Baali, 2015).

1.1.1. Incidence in Pakistan

Most common malignancy of women in the world is breast cancer with approximately 1 million new cases yearly. Breast cancer is also the second leading cause of death in females worldwide (McPherson et al., 2000, Asif et al., 2014). Karachi Cancer Registry (KCR) for Karachi South reported breast cancer incidence and ASR (per 100,000) as 33.1% and 51.7 respectively based upon data from 1995 to 1997. Incidence was calculated using Karachi South population as per 1998 population (Bhurgri et al., 2000b). KCR reprinted an updated data from January 1995 to December 2002 presenting an incidence of 34.6% and ASR (per 100,000) 69.1 (Bhurgri, 2004). KIRAN Hospital, Karachi reported ASR (per 100,000) as 0.97 and 38.2 for males and females respectively. (Hanif et al., 2009)

Reported ASR (per 100,000) for breast cancer in Hyderabad from January 1998 to December 2002 is 22.4, significantly less than Karachi (Bhurgri et al., 2005). ASR of breast cancer in Larkana and Quetta is 20.6 and 11.8 respectively (Moore et al., 2010). INMOL Hospital, Lahore reported breast cancer frequency as 23% of all visited cancer patients and 41% of all female cancer based upon data January 2000 to December 2009 and female to male ratio was 100:2 (Khokher et al., 2012). Male breast carcinoma has reported incidence of 0.7% of all cancers and 1.1% of all malignancies in males in northern areas of Pakistan. Incidence among both genders is 5.9% and male to female ratio is 1:16. Data was retrospectively analysed from 1992 to 2001 (Jamal et al., 2006).

1.1.2. Current Treatments

Breast cancer is usually treated with surgery in combination with chemotherapy, hormone therapy or radiotherapy depending upon cancer stage. Breast cancer may be managed by surgical removal of tumour or lump with surrounding tissues and sentinel lymph nodes. Removing a sentinel lymph node limits metastasis of primary tumour (Donker et al., 2014). Lumpectomy, mastectomy and quadrantectomy are the surgical techniques applied for surgical removal of tumour depending upon size and location of tumour. Radiotherapy is usually given to a patient after surgical removal of tumour to destroy tumour microenvironment in tissues and lymph nodes (Donker et al., 2014). Radiotherapy after surgery reduces the chances of recurrence of cancer and mortality in patients (McGale et al., 2014).

Chemotherapeutic agents induce cytotoxicity generally by targeting DNA content of the cells. Adjuvant chemotherapy is used to kill cancer and carcinogenic cells (even non-detectable with imaging techniques) present after surgery to prevent metastasis in future. Neoadjuvant chemotherapy is used to treat cancer cells before surgical removal of cancers. Primarily, this type of chemotherapy is employed in locally advanced cancers. Chemotherapy is also used to treat metastasised breast cancers either at diagnosis or after initial treatment. Anthracyclines, taxanes, 5-flourouracil, cyclophosphamide and carboplatin are the most common chemotherapeutic agents to treat breast cancer.

Targeted and hormone therapies are also available for breast cancers. Targeted therapies include CDK inhibitors, kinase inhibitors or monoclonal antibodies etc. For example, HER2 positive breast cancers may be treated using targeted monoclonal antibodies like trastuzumab (Raychaudhuri et al., 2018), pertuzumab (Tono et al., 2018) or ado-trastuzumab emtansine (Jhaveri et al., 2018) or kinase inhibitors like

lapatinib (Tada et al., 2018) or neratinib (Xu et al., 2018) etc. CDK4 and CDK6 inhibitors may also be targeted against ER or PR positive breast cancers (Abraham et al., 2018).

ER and PR positive breast cancers are usually treated by hormone therapies. As high levels of oestrogen or progesterone help breast cancer cells to grow, so this therapy is used to inhibit the supportive effects of these hormones for the cancer cells. Some of the hormone based therapeutic agents being used to block oestrogen receptors present on cancer cells include tamoxifen, toremifene, fulvestrant etc (Yin et al., 2018).

1.2. Colorectal Cancer

Colorectal cancer (CRC) is the third most common cancer in the world present in 13.2% and 12.7% of men and women respectively and causes 550,000 cancer deaths annually in the world (Stewart and Wild, 2017, Bretthauer, 2011, Van Cutsem et al., 2014). There are multiple genetic and epigenetic factors as risk to CRC development. Major risks factors involved are diet (alcohol, red and processed meat), obesity and lack of physical activity. Familial adenomatous polyposis and hereditary nonpolyposis are two autosomal dominant conditions associated with high risk of CRC (Thorat and Cuzick, 2013).

Faecal occult blood test (FOBT) and flexible sigmoidoscopy are used as screening tools for CRC. FOBT and flexible sigmoidoscopy reduce mortality rate by ~16% and ~30% respectively. Sigmoidoscopy and colonoscopy both may be used for diagnosing CRC. Colonoscopy has an advantage as it can be applied for removing polyps; small polyps may be discarded but large polyps should undergo histopathological analysis, so a diagnosis may be confirmed. Beside histopathological analysis, radiological tools

of CT and PET scans are also used in establishing diagnosis. TNM and Duke staging systems are used for staging of CRC.

1.2.1. Incidence in Pakistan

In Pakistan, reported prevalence of CRC (Karachi, Pakistan) is 3.9% (ASR = 5.1 per 100,000) and 3.1% (ASR = 5.2 per 100,000) among males and females respectively (Bhurgri et al., 2000a). Hasan et al. reported prevalence of CRC as 2.6% in urban dwellers of Karachi (Hasan et al., 2017). Sarwar and Saqib reported prevalence of CRC as 3.6% for year 2012 while combining both genders (Sarwar and Saqib, 2017).

1.2.2. Current Treatments

CRC is treated in combination or individually by surgery, radiotherapy and chemotherapy depending upon staging of cancer. Curative surgery is the suitable option if cancer has a reasonable response to chemotherapy. Surgery is the most common and widespread initial treatment option for CRC. During the surgery, tumour mass along with the surrounding margins and nearby lymph nodes are removed. For most of the cases with stage I and II CRC, surgery alone is enough as treatment. Adjuvant chemotherapy is not supported for local colon and rectal cancers; however, lymph node metastasized cancers undergo. Strongest indication for adjuvant therapy is metastasis to regional lymph nodes. Fluorouracil is one of the effective systematic treatment options available for CRC in combination with leucovorin. Other available compounds are capecitabine, irinotecan, and oxaliplatin (Soreide et al., 2011). Neoadjuvant chemotherapy is supported in rectal cancer and decreases risk of recurrence to ~50% in stage II and III of rectal cancer but it primarily depends upon stage of the cancer (Soreide et al., 2011).

1.3. Cell Cycle and Cancers

1.3.1. Cell cycle

Cell cycle is the sequence of events held in nucleus of any living cell from DNA duplication to cell division. Cell cycle in one cell divides parent cell into two daughter cells. Cell cycle is highly complex process as it copies all features of DNA to daughter cells. Cell cycle in any eukaryotic cell has following stages:

- G₀-Phase: when cell is not dividing
- G₁-Phase: cell size grows, mRNA and proteins are synthesized
- S-Phase: replicated DNA is synthesized
- G₂-Phase: spindle formation
- M-Phase: parent cell divides in two genetically identical cells

Cyclins, cyclin dependent kinases (CDKs) and CDKs inhibitors regulate cell cycle during all these stages.

1.3.1.1. Checkpoints in cell cycle

There are three checkpoints in cell cycle to regulate above mentioned stages during cell division as detailed briefly below:

- G₁ checkpoint: This checkpoint checks for pre-division requirements including cell size, nutrients, required growth factors and any DNA damage that may lead to mutations in daughter cells.
- G₂ checkpoint: This checkpoint checks if DNA replication is completed.
- Spindle assembly checkpoint: This checkpoint checks if chromosomes are attached to spindle.

1.3.2. Cell cycle in carcinogenesis

Cancer is known for uncontrolled proliferation of cells. Cell proliferation is always controlled by controlled cell cycle process. Cell cycle deregulation leads to extensive

proliferation of cancer cells. In this cell cycle deregulation, above mentioned checkpoints do not perform their normal functions. Other changes are induced by following regulatory proteins:

- Cyclins: In cancer cells, cyclins are overexpressed and are not degraded. Instead, cyclins remain associated with CDKs leading to continuous cell cycle process.
- CDKs: Like cyclins, CDKs are also overexpressed in cancer cells. CDKs also avoid inhibition by CDK inhibitors and keep P activated.
- CDKs Inhibitors: CDKs inhibitors in cancer cells suffer deletion in genes thus leading to complete absence or decreased concentrations than required.

1.3.3. Cell cycle targeting drugs

As per described importance of cell cycle in cancers, many drugs are available which target cell cycle in cancer cells. These drugs include flavopiridol, AT-7519 and BMS-387032 etc.

1.4. Availability of New Therapeutic Compounds

Combinations of surgical measures, radiotherapy and chemotherapeutic agents are not highly successful against advanced stages of breast cancer and CRC as reflected by a low five years survival rates. At the same time, available chemotherapeutic agents present side effects in the forms of alopecia, gastrointestinal toxicity (causing mouth sores, loss of appetite, nausea, vomiting, and diarrhoea) or bone marrow toxicity (causing leukopenia, thrombocytopenia, and anaemia) (Wu et al., 2005). All these side effects cause systematic changes in patients undergoing chemotherapy thus resulting in poor life quality. Furthermore, many of the patients undergoing chemotherapy need frequent transfusions due to higher haemolytic activity in the body. The situation highlights the need for searching chemotherapeutic agents that

cause minimum haemolytic/gastrointestinal toxicity and induces tumour cell specific toxic effects. In this context, alkylphospholipids comprise a promising class of compounds with significant potential as anti-cancer agents.

1.5. Alkylphospholipids

Alkylphospholipids are synthetic compounds with proven anti-cancer anti-proliferative activities. ALPs comprise glycosylated ether lipids and glycosidated phospholipids. Current understanding about mechanism of action is their ability to interfere with lipid haemostasis because of similarity with the endogenous lipids. ALPs target lipid rafts in cell membrane and alter lipid-linked signals resulting in apoptosis and cytostatic impact (Ríos-Marco et al., 2017). ALPs held an advantage over conventional anti-cancer agents as they act by targeting cell membrane phospholipids instead of targeting DNA of cancer cells. At clinical concentrations, these ALPs insert a micelle in lipid bilayer to cause biophysical disturbance. This interference with cell membrane metabolism triggers destructive cellular pathways (de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013).

1.5.1. Mechanisms of action of Alkylphospholipids

Proposed key mechanisms of action of ALPs are as following:

- **Inactivation of PKC:** PKC are usually activated for long times and play vital role in signal transduction. ALPs inhibit PKC leading to decrease in signal transduction cascades required for proliferating cancer cells (de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013, Ali et al., 2016).
- **Inactivation of Akt:** Akt, a serine/threonine kinase, plays important roles in several cell survival and growth pathways. ALPs stop Akt activation either by structural changes in membrane microdomains thus putting a halt to growth factor

signalling or by displacement of PIP2 or PIP3, the Akt ligands (de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013).

- **Phosphatidylcholines inhibition:** ALPs inhibit synthesis of phosphatidylcholines in endoplasmic reticulum through modulation of CHOP/GADD 153 (a transcription factor) and play a pivotal role in apoptotic process. (de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013, Kaleagasioglu and Berger, 2014).
- **Perturbation in cholesterol haemostasis:** ALPs accumulate in lipid rafts in cell membrane and perturbate cholesterol haemostasis. This perturbation in haemostasis uptakes more ALPs and leads to apoptosis (Kaleagasioglu and Berger, 2014, de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013).
- **Apoptosis induction due to FAS redistribution:** Redistribution of FAS in lipid rafts stimulates FAS/CD95 forming death inducing signalling complex (DISC) leading to apoptosis (de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013).

1.5.2. Classification of Alkylphospholipids

Generation I: Lysophosphatidylcholines (LysoPC) are endogenous component of cell membrane and formed by hydrolysis of phosphatidylcholines by phospholipases and modulates several signalling pathways. First compound termed as ALP was edelfosine synthesized by replacing glycerol C1 ester bond by an ether bond and addition of ether linked methyl group at C2 position of LysoPC. Edelfosine showed immunomodulatory properties and antiproliferative activity *in vitro* and *in vivo* but cytotoxic assays revealed a less selective nature for tumour cells. Edelfosine has metabolic instability, high haemolytic potential and gastrointestinal toxicity and being used to purge bone marrow of acute leukaemia patients (de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013).

Generation II: Two research groups of UK and Germany synthesized miltefosine independent of each other in late 80s; one group was working on platelet aggregation and other was searching for anti-tumour compound. Miltefosine is considered as prototype of a class of ALPs named alkylphosphocholines. This compound with appreciable cytotoxic activity like previous ALPs was highly haemolytic and showed gastrointestinal toxicity as well, thus limiting its maximum tolerated dose (MTD) upto 200mg (de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013).

Generation III: Replacement of choline group with piperidine group revealed a stable compound with a half-life of approximately 140 hours named perifosine. Perifosine was having a major advantage of stability over previous ALPs. Phase I clinical trials revealed cytotoxic potential against a variety of tumours but maximum MTD was not more than 200 mg/day due to various side-effects (de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013).

Generation IV: Recently, two more analogues of ALPs having 22 carbons chain are synthesized named erucylphosphocholine (ErPC) and erufosine (ErPC3). Both of these compounds are relatively less haemolytic than previous ALPs because these form lamellar structures in aqueous solutions instead of micelles like other ALPs. Another important property owned by these compounds is the ability to cross blood-brain barrier. Erufosine is even less haemolytic than ErPC3 allowing intravenous administration with the possibility of monotherapy or combination regimens while achieving clinically relevant dosage at low concentrations.

1.5.3. Clinical Applications of Alkylphospholipids

Parasites: Miltefosine is the only treatment available for leishmaniasis currently; however, its efficiency varies depending upon species of leishmania and geographical

regions. Other ALPs like edelfosine and perifosine have also been found effective to treat leishmaniasis, *L. braziliensis*, *L. infantum*, *L. major* and *L. amazonensis* species (Cabrera-Serra et al., 2008). Trypanosoma species i.e., *T. cruzi* and *T. brucei* cause Chagas disease and sleeping sickness respectively. Various *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies revealed that miltefosine is significantly toxic for *T. cruzi* and *T. brucei* (Luna et al., 2009, de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013).

Fungal infections: Fungal infection (also known as mycosis) is the 4th most common disease in human worldwide (Hay et al., 2014). Widmer *et al.* treated *Scedosporium prolificans* and *Cryptococcus spp.* with miltefosine and observed significant fungicidal activity. *In vitro* study also revealed fungicidal activity of miltefosine against *T. rubrum*, *T. mentagrophytes*, *T. tonsurans*, *T. soudanese*, *T. violaceum*, *M. canis*, *M. gypseum*, *M. cookei*, and *E. floccosum*. (Tong et al., 2007)

Bacterial infections: Applications in parasitosis and mycosis encouraged scientists to investigate ALPs in bacterial infections. Miltefosine was found to be with anti-bacterial activity against *Streptococcus spp.* It is also found to be sensitive against *Staphylococcus aureus*. ALPs are not sensitive to gram negative bacteria (Obando et al., 2007, Llull et al., 2007).

Intraocular lens coating: ALPs can also be applied with lens to inhibit epithelial cell growth on lens. A concentration of 1mM is biologically compatible for intraocular use. This novel application may be possible in near future after studying biological and physicochemical properties of ALPs (Eibl et al., 2009, Eibl et al., 2013).

Chronic spontaneous urticarial: ALPs especially miltefosine inhibit inflammatory mediators release by human mast cells. These inflammatory mediators cause chronic urticaria in many patients which is not treatable with conventional therapies.

Miltefosine was used to treat urticaria and other allergies in humans with some side effects including abdominal discomfort, nausea and vomiting (Magerl et al., 2013).

1.5.4. Applications in Cancer Treatment

Utilization of edelfosine (1st generation) and miltefosine (2nd generation) as anti-cancer agents is limited mainly because of metabolic instability, high haemolytic activity and gastrointestinal toxicity. These side effects restrict the maximum tolerated daily drug dose and usage as a systematic therapeutic agent. So far, edelfosine and miltefosine are being used in bone-marrow purging in patients with acute leukaemia. (van Blitterswijk and Verheij, 2013, de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013)

Perifosine (3rd generation) has been tested in phase I clinical trials for taxane-resistant, platinum-resistant and refractory epithelial ovarian cancer (Fu et al., 2012). Phase II clinical trials of perifosine are completed for advanced renal carcinoma, advanced soft tissue sarcoma, androgen independent prostate cancer, head and neck cancer, metastatic colorectal cancer, metastatic melanoma, metastatic pancreatic adenocarcinoma and recurrent prostatic cancer (de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013). Phase II trials are also completed for relapsed, refractory and Waldenstrom's macroglobulinemia (Ghobrial et al., 2010). Phase III clinical trials have been successfully conducted for treatment of relapsed and refractory multiple myeloma using perifosine (de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013).

Investigations about anti-neoplastic potential of most advanced agent of ALPs (erufosine, 4th generation) is limited to pre-clinical studies so far and increased understanding about its anti-cancer properties will foster the evaluations in phase I trials. *In vitro* investigations are successfully conducted against acute myeloid leukaemia, astrocytoma, glioblastoma, multiple myeloma, and oral squamous cell

carcinoma (Kapoor et al., 2012, Yosifov et al., 2011, Königs et al., 2010, de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013).

1.6. Erufosine

1.6.1. Structural Changes

Lysophosphatidylcholines (LysoPC) are considered as ancestors of ALPs. Ebil synthesized first ALP (edelfosine) in late 60s by replacing glycerol group with ether group at C1 and an ether linked methyl group at C2 (de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013). Edelfosine was found to be having high anti-proliferative activity against different cancer cells *in vitro* and *in vivo* but use of edelfosine became limited due to gastrointestinal toxicity, high haemolytic activity and metabolic instability. ALPs reached at a clinically important level in 1980s by the synthesis of a new ALP analogue without glycerol motif, miltefosine. Miltefosine was found to be anti-proliferative just like previous ALPs but with haemolytic and gastrointestinal toxicity limiting its intravenous and oral applications (Dorlo et al., 2012, de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013).

Choline moiety of miltefosine was replaced by a heterocyclic piperidine group formed perifosine. Addition of piperidine group to perifosine increased its half-life by 140 hours much more than miltefosine, but toxicological profile was almost the same as miltefosine (Hilgard et al., 1997). Two ALPs, erufosine and erucylphosphocholine were synthesized in late 90s containing 22 carbon chains with ω -9-cis double bond (Berger et al., 1998, Kaufmann-Kolle et al., 1996).

Figure 1: Structural description of different classes of ALPs
(de Almeida Pachioni et al., 2013)

1.6.2. Characteristics of Erufosine

The characteristics of erufosine differentiating it from previous ALPs are described below:

- Structural modification of erufosine made it less haemolytic than previous ALPs thus making its intravenous application feasible. This characteristic of erufosine is likely due to formation of lamellar structures in aqueous solution rather than micelles like previous ALPs (van Blitterswijk and Verheij, 2013).
- Erufosine can cross blood-brain barrier thus enabling treatment of brain tumours. An *in vitro* study revealed glioblastoma cells sensitive to erufosine (Jendrossek et al., 2002).
- Erufosine is less toxic for bone marrow than previous ALPs, which highlight the possibility of high applicable intravenous doses as monotherapy or in combination regimens (Bagley et al., 2011).

1.6.3. Erufosine in Pre-Clinical Cancer Settings

1.6.3.1. Acute Myeloid Leukaemia

Fiegl *et al.* applied erufosine to HL60 cells and performed cell death analysis by using Annexin V and measurement of activated caspase 3. WST-1 analysis revealed lethal concentration (Moore *et al.*, 2010) of erufosine as 7.4 µg/ml after 24 hours and 3.2 µg/ml after 72 hours in HL60 cells. Erufosine's LC in AML patient samples was found as 30.1 and 80.6 µg/ml (Fiegl *et al.*, 2008).

1.6.3.2. Breast Cancer

Dineva and co-workers studied erufosine for its antiproliferative activity against breast cancer both *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Two breast cancer cell lines MCF-7 and MDA-MB-231 were used for *in vitro* study and found to be equally sensitive to erufosine at IC₅₀ of 40 µM. An *in vivo* study on induced carcinoma in rats revealed more than 85% remission of tumour with only 7% body weight loss. It is also concluded that erufosine influence PI3K/Akt and Ras/Raf/MAPK pathways by decreasing the phosphorylation (Dineva *et al.*, 2012).

1.6.3.3. Chronic Lymphocytic Leukaemia

Erufosine was found to induce apoptosis in chronic lymphocytic leukaemia cells at inhibitory concentration (IC) 50 of 22 µM (Königs *et al.*, 2010). Retinoblastoma signalling pathway was also found to be essential for antineoplastic activity of erufosine (Zaharieva *et al.*, 2014).

1.6.3.4. Chronic Myeloid Leukemic Cells

BV-173 and K-562 cell lines were found to be sensitive to erufosine. Sensitivity of these cell lines was found to be dependent upon retinoblastoma signalling pathway at a dose lower than IC₅₀. However, apoptosis is not dependent on retinoblastoma at higher doses of erufosine (Yosifov *et al.*, 2007). It is also reported that erufosine in

combination with antisense oligonucleotide synergistically inhibit growth of CML cells, however, it does not affect growth of normal cells (Konstantinov et al., 2002).

1.6.3.5. Colorectal Cancer Cells

Human and rat CRC cell lines have been studied for sensitivity to erufosine. Human cell line, SW480 and rat cell line CC531 were found to be sensitive to erufosine at IC_{50} of 3.4 and 25.4 μ M respectively (Kaleağasıoğlu and Berger, 2014).

1.6.3.6. Multiple Myeloma Cells

Multiple myeloma cell lines: RPMI-8226, U-266 and OPM-2 have been studied for sensitivity towards erufosine. Erufosine was found to have an antimyeloma potential (Yosifov et al., 2011). RPMI-8226 was found to be most sensitive cell line towards erufosine while U-266 was the least sensitive with IC_{50} values of 3.2 and 16.2 μ M respectively (Yosifov et al., 2009).

1.6.3.7. Oral Squamous Carcinoma Cells

Erufosine has the potential to induce apoptosis, autophagy and G2 cell cycle arrest in oral squamous carcinoma cell lines (HN-5 and FaDu) (Kapoor et al., 2012, Ansari et al., 2017).

1.6.3.8. Prostate Cancer Cells

Human Prostate cancer cell lines: DU-145, LNCaP and PC3 have been studied for sensitivity towards erufosine. DU-145 was found to be most sensitive while all the three cell lines showed increased sensitivity to erufosine when combined with radiotherapy (Rudner et al., 2010).

CHAPTER 2: OBJECTIVES

The objectives of the current research were:

1. To explore the expressional changes in cell cycle relevant genes induced by erufosine in breast and colorectal cancer cells.
2. To design the signalling pathway for cell cycle arrest imposed by erufosine in breast and colorectal cancer cells by using *Ingenuity Pathways Analysis* software.

CHAPTER 3: MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Methodology for Preliminary Work

3.1.1. Cell Culture

Two human breast cancer cell lines i.e., MDA-MB-231 and MCF-7 and two colon adenocarcinoma cancer cell lines i.e., SW480 and SW620 were cultured in RPMI-1640 medium, supplemented with 10% foetal bovine serum (FBS), 2mM L-glutamate, streptomycin (100µg/ml) and penicillin (100IU/ml). All the materials required for cell culture were purchased from Invitrogen (see *Appendix 1* for details). Cells were incubated at standard incubation conditions (5% CO₂, 37°C, humidified environment) and passaged regularly (2-3 times/week) for logarithmic cell growth.

3.1.2. MTT Dye Reduction Assay

MTT dye reduction assay was performed to observe cell viability and proliferation following treatment with erufosine. All four cell lines were seeded in 96 well plates at pre-optimized cell densities (4000 cells/well/100µl media) and treated with various concentrations of erufosine (0.75-100 µM) for three-time points i.e., 24, 48 and 72 hours. Following the treatment intervals, MTT solution (10mg/ml in PBS) was added (10µl/well) and cells were incubated at standard conditions for 3 hours. Formazan crystals, formed by the viable cells, were dissolved by adding 10µl of acidic solvent (0.04 N HCL in 2-propanol) in each well. Optical density was measured using an ELISA reader (AnthosMicrosysteme, Krefeld, Germany) at 560 nm and 690 nm reference filter. Cell survival rates were calculated as percentage of the untreated cells while IC values were calculated by GraphPad Prism 6 software.

3.1.3. Cell Cycle Arrest Analysis

To see the effects of erufosine on cell cycle, propidium iodide (PI) based staining of DNA and flow cytometry (FACS) methodology were used. The cells were harvested

after exposure with erufosine (IC₂₅, IC₅₀, and IC₇₅) for 48 hours and fixed with ice cold 70% ethanol at 4°C for 2 hours. The cells were washed with PBS and RNA was digested by addition of RNase A (1mg/ml). The cells were incubated at 37°C for 30 minutes and PI was added (50 µg/ml). Cells were placed in dark at room temperature for 15-30 minutes and analysed in FACS canto (BD, Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA). Ten thousand cells (events) per sample were analysed to study distribution of the cells in different phases of the cell cycle (G0/G1, S, and G2/M). Relative percentages were determined by Modfit LT software and compared with untreated cells as controls.

3.2. Study Design

This study was an experimental study.

3.3. Research Settings

This study was conducted in Allied Health Sciences Department, Chemical Pathology and Department of Human Genetics and Molecular Biology, University of Health Sciences, Lahore. Subsequent support, where needed in experimental work, was obtained from our collaborator (DKFZ).

3.4. Duration

The duration of project was 1 year after the date of approval.

3.5. Source Material

Erufosine was provided by our collaborator, Prof. Martin R. Berger, head of toxicology and chemotherapy unit, DKFZ, Heidelberg, Germany. Selected breast (MDA-MB-231 and MCF-7) and colorectal (SW480 and SW620) cancer cells were cultured in 6-well cell culture plates (150,000cells/well/2ml medium) and treated next day with erufosine (IC₂₅, IC₅₀, IC₇₅) for 48 hours. Afterwards, the cell palettes were

collected by trypsinizing the cells and stored at -80°C . Likewise, the cell palettes of untreated cells as controls were also collected and stored in similar conditions.

3.6. Sample Size

To investigate the expressional modulations in 84 cell cycle relevant genes by using ready-made cell cycle panels and qRT-PCR methodology, breast (MDA-MB-231) and CRC (SW620) cell lines were treated with erufosine (48 hours/ IC_{75}). Sample distribution for this purpose is shown in *Table 1*, while complete methodology will be described in subsequent section (3.7.5).

Cells	MDA-MB-231		SW620	
Groups	Untreated control	Erufosine treated (IC_{75})	Untreated control	Erufosine treated (IC_{75})

Table 1: Sample distribution for qRT-PCR involving cell cycle panels

As per description about the cell cycle panel mentioned on the manufacturer website (Qiagen, Provide [LINK](#)), there are 19 genes included in the panel which are mainly related to G2/M phase of the cell cycle (*Table 2*). Based on the cell cycle panel results, three most altered genes from this list were selected and expressional profiles were identified by qRT-PCRs in breast (MDA-MB-231, MCF-7) and CRC cells (SW480, SW620) treated with various concentrations of erufosine (IC_{25} , IC_{50} , and IC_{75}) for 48 hours (*Table 2: Genes associated with G2/M phase of the cell cycle*). Complete methodology will be described in subsequent section (3.7.7).

ANAPC2	BCCIP	BIRC5	CCNA2	CCNB1	CCNG1	CCNH	CCNT1	CDC25A	CDK5R1
CDK5RAP1	CDK7	CDKN3	CKS1B	CKS2	GTSE1	KPNA2	MNAT1	SERTAD1	

Table 2: Genes associated with G2/M phase of the cell cycle

Cell Line	MDA-MB-231				MCF-7				SW480				SW620			
Groups	UC		Treated		UC		Treated		UC		Treated		UC		Treated	
Erufosine	0	IC 25	IC 50	IC 75	0	IC 25	IC 50	IC 75	0	IC 25	IC 50	IC 75	0	IC 25	IC 50	IC 75

Table 3: Sample distribution for selected G2/M phase associated 3 genes (UC: untreated control)

3.7. Experimental Procedure

3.7.1. RNA Extraction

Total RNA was extracted from the control and treated cell palettes by using RNeasy Mini Kit (Qiagen), while following the manufacture’s protocol. A descriptive layout of the protocol is presented in **Figure 2**.

Total RNA Extraction was carried out using spin column technology				
Process		Steps		Reagents
Cell lysis	Cell line(s)		↓	Buffer RLT
	Lyse & Homogenize			
RNA isolation using spin column method	Selective RNA binding to RNeasy membrane		↓	Ethanol
	RNeasy Mini Spin Column			
RNA purification	3X washing	Removal of contaminants	↓	Wash Buffer
	Elution			Elution Buffer
		Total RNA	↓	

Figure 2: Total RNA extraction method

3.7.2. RNA Quantification

RNA was quantified by using spectrophotometric system, Nanodrop ND 2000.

3.7.3. cDNA Synthesis

A total of 1000ng extracted RNA was used to synthesize cDNA (20 μ l) by using Maxima Reverse Transcriptase (Thermo Scientific). Detail about the Maxima Reverse Transcriptase Kit's method is described in .

Reaction Component	Concentration	Volume
Total RNA	1000ng	Varied as per concentration of extracted RNA from the samples
Primer (Oligo dT)	100pmol	1 μ l
dNTP Mix	0.5mM	1 μ l
Water	Nuclease Free	To make a total of 20 μ l cDNA
RT Buffer	5X	4 μ l
Ribolock RNase Inhibitor	20U	0.5 μ l
Maxima Reverse Transcriptase	200U	1 μ l
Incubation Conditions		
Step 1	Step 2	Step 3
50°C (30 minutes)	85°C (5 minutes)	10°C (30 minutes)

Table 4: cDNA synthesis reaction recipe and incubation conditions

3.7.4. Verification of cDNA synthesis

A PCR based amplification of a reference gene (GAPDH) was performed to verify the prepared cDNA samples. PCR recipe and cycling conditions are described in

Table 5 and **Figure 3** respectively. Amplified products were visualized by agarose gel electrophoresis methodology. Electrophoresis conditions were 100 Volts for 45 minutes while using a 2.5% agarose gel prepared in TAE buffer. A total of 10 μ l for each amplified sample was loaded for electrophoresis along with 3 μ l of DNA marker (50 bp/Fermentas).

Sr. No.	Reaction Components	Amount per reaction
1	Master mix (2X)	5 μ l
2	Primers (GAPDH, Sequence: Table 2) 10pmol	0.5 μ l
3	Nuclease free Water (Thermofisher)	3 μ l
4	Total volume	9 μ l
5	cDNA	1 μ l

Table 5: Amount of PCR components per reaction for cDNA verification

Figure 3: PCR cycling conditions of confirmatory cDNA PCR

3.7.5. Qiagen Cell Cycle Panel

Qiagen RT² Profiler PCR Array Human Cell Cycle Panel (Qiagen) was used for expression analysis of cell cycle relevant genes. This panel contains primers and probes for 84 cell cycle relevant genes along with seven reference genes to normalize the data. In addition, 3 RT-negative controls to monitor the residual genomic DNA from RNA extraction step and 3 RT-positive controls to check the quality of reverse transcription are also included in this panel. Untreated control and treated (IC₇₅/48 hours) cDNA samples from metastatic cell lines (MDA-MB- 231/breast cancer, SW620/CRC), showing higher sensitivity towards erufosine exposure (**Table 6**,

results section) were used in these ready-made qRT-PCR assays. Briefly, a total of 20µl cDNA sample prepared from 1000 ng extracted total RNA was used for each 96-well ready-made plate along with 1000 µl SybrGreen and nuclease free water to make a volume of 20µl/well. Reaction conditions for the ready-made panel assays are mentioned in **Figure 4**. Plate map and complete list of genes included in the panel are shown in **Appendix 2** and **Appendix 3** respectively. After amplification procedures by qRT-PCRs and normalization of the data sets, fold changes were calculated by the $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method by comparing Cq (quantification cycle) values of experimental (erufosine treated) and untreated control samples.

Figure 4: Real-Time PCR conditions for panel-based amplifications of cell cycle genes
3.7.6. Primer Designing

As per Qiagen cell cycle panel, genes associated to G2/M phase of cell cycle are mentioned in **Table 2**. In view of the cell cycle panel results, 3 most altered genes (up or down-regulated) from this table were CCNA2, CCNB1, and CDKN3. Primers, for these selected genes, were designed by choosing gene sequence from NCBI Gene bank and using Primer3 software. Primer sequences are given in **Table 6**.

Gene	Primer Sequence (F.)	Primer Sequence (R.)	GC%
CDKN3	CCCTCAGAAATGATCGGAAA	CAGCTTGCGATAACCAAAGG	45 & 50
CCNB1	CCTCCTTGAAAGCAAACAG	TCAAGAGGGACCAATGGTTT	50 & 45
CCNA2	CACTTCCTTCGGAGAGCATC	AGAAGGAGGAAAGTGCACCA	55 & 50
β -Actin	TCCACCTTCCAGCAGATGTG	GCATTTGCGGTGGACGAT	55 & 55
GAPDH	ACGGATTTGGTCGTATTGGG	CGCTCCTGGAAGATGGTGAT	50 & 55

Table 6: Primer sequence for amplification of cell cycle related and reference genes

3.7.7. qRT-PCR for Selected Genes

qRT-PCR was performed by using SybrGreen fluorescence dye for selected 3 genes (as mentioned above) by using cDNA samples from four cell lines (MDA-MB- 231, MCF-7, SW480, SW620) treated with three concentrations of erufosine (IC_{25} , IC_{50} or IC_{75}) for 48 hours. Sample distribution for these qRT-PCR experiments are shown in **Table 3**. $2^{-\Delta\Delta CT}$ method was used to find out expressional changes in three selected genes in control and erufosine treated samples. β -actin was used as reference gene in these experiments. This series of PCR based amplification of selected genes was performed to elaborate and validate our results from Qiagen cell cycle panel. Additionally, it was shown that erufosine has the ability to induce expressional modifications in cell cycle related genes in primary (SW480, MCF7) as well as metastatic (SW620, MDA-MB-231) cancer cell lines.

3.7.8. Designing Cell Cycle Pathway

Data obtained from the cell cycle panel was used to design a signalling pathway with the help of *Ingenuity Pathways Analysis* (IPA) software at core facility of DKFZ, Germany to explain cell cycle arrest imposed by erufosine in the target cells.

CHAPTER 4: RESULTS

4.1. Preliminary Results

4.1.1. Erufosine Toxicity

Toxic effects of erufosine against breast and CRC cells were studied by MTT (3-[4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2,5 diphenyltetrazolium bromide) dye reduction assay as described above (3.1.2.). ICs were identified by the help of GraphPad Prism 6 software, while IC₅₀ values of erufosine against the selected cancer cells are given in

Table 6.

	Breast Cancer Cells		Colorectal Cancer Cells	
	MDA-MB-231	MCF-7	SW480	SW620
24 h	8 μ M	8.2 μ M	5.8 μ M	5.5 μ M
48 h	12.5 μ M	17 μ M	10.1 μ M	10 μ M
72 h	20 μ M	40 μ M	15.8 μ M	20.1 μ M

Table 6: IC₅₀ concentrations after 24, 48 and 72 hours of erufosine treatment

4.1.2. Effects on Cell Cycle

Effects of erufosine on cell cycle of the cancer cells were determined by PI based fluorescent staining and FACS analysis as described earlier (3.1.3). Erufosine induced arrest in G2/M phase of cell cycle in selected four cancer cell lines. The cytostatic effects were more pronounced in metastatic cancer cell lines of breast (MDA-MB-231) and CRC (SW620). Alterations in cell cycle distributions after exposing the cells with various concentrations of erufosine (IC₂₅, IC₅₀ or IC₇₅) for 48 hours are shown in

Table 7.

	Breast Cancer Cells								Colorectal Cancer Cells							
Cell Line	MDA-MB-231				MCF-7				SW480				SW620			
Erufosine	0	IC ₂₅	IC ₅₀	IC ₇₅	0	IC ₂₅	IC ₅₀	IC ₇₅	0	IC ₂₅	IC ₅₀	IC ₇₅	0	IC ₂₅	IC ₅₀	IC ₇₅
Phase G0-G1 (%)	53	50	29	17	36	32	26	22	43	33	29	20	32	30	18	12
Phase G2-M (%)	23	27	43	61	31	37	39	44	16	23	26	28	22	25	33	39
Phase S (%)	13	9	7	3	13	11	8	7	17	17	18	20	28	19	23	17

Table 7: Cell cycle distributions (%) after 48 hours of treatment with erufosine

Figure 5: Effects of erufosine on cell cycle of breast and colorectal cancer cells

4.2. cDNA Verification

Total extracted RNA from untreated controls and treated samples was used to synthesize cNDA and verified subsequently by PCR based amplification of a reference gene (*GAPDH*) as mentioned earlier (3.7.4). Amplified products were visualized by agarose gel electrophoresis methodology (*Figure 6* and *Figure 7*). Duplicated sample of MDA-MB-231 (well#7) and MCF-7 (well#14) did not show

amplified products, which is may be due to pipetting error while adding cDNA samples or prepared master-mix to corresponding wells of the tubes (**Figure 7**).

Figure 6: Electrophoresed cDNA of SW480 & SW620

Sample distribution (left to right): Well 1: DNA marker (50bp) Well 2-9: SW480 (Untreated Control, IC₂₅, IC₅₀, and IC₇₅ (each sample is in duplicate) Well 10-17: SW620 (Untreated Control, IC₂₅, IC₅₀, and IC₇₅ (each sample is in duplicate) Well 18-19: RT -ve and PCR -ve controls

Figure 7: Electrophoresed cDNA of MDA-MB-231 & MCF-7

Sample distribution (left to right): Well 1: DNA marker (50bp) Well 2-9: MDA-MB-231 (Untreated Control, IC₂₅, IC₅₀, and IC₇₅ (each sample is in duplicate) Well 10-17: MCF-7 (Untreated Control, IC₂₅, IC₅₀, and IC₇₅ (each sample is in duplicate) Well 18-19: RT -ve and PCR -ve controls

4.3. RT-Panel Results

Human Cell Cycle panels were used to study expression changes in 84 cell cycle relevant genes imposed by erufosine in breast (MDA-MB-231) and CRC (SW620) cells. Following the real-time PCR based amplification procedures, $2^{\Delta\Delta CT}$ method was used to determine differences in gene expression among erufosine treated and untreated controls. Changes in all 84 genes relevant to cell cycle are presented in **Figure 8** and **Figure 9** while genes with two-fold or more change in expression are presented in **Figure 10** and **Figure 11**.

Figure 8: Erufosine induced changes in cell cycle relevant genes in MDA-MB-231 cells

Figure 9: Erufosine induced changes in cell cycle relevant genes in SW 620 cells

Figure 10: Two-fold or higher expressional change in erufosine treated MDA-MB-231 cells

Figure 11: Two-fold or higher expressional change in erufosine treated SW620 cells

4.3.1: Expressional Changes in Breast Cancer Cells

Among 84 genes of cell cycle panel, 83% (68/82) were down-regulated while remaining 17% (18/82) showed up-regulation in MDA-MB-231 cells after exposure with erufosine (IC₇₅/48 hours). In addition, two genes from the panel (CDKN2A and

CDKN2B) showed a very late expression ($C_q > 38$ cycles) and were not considered in the follow-up analysis. Among the altered genes, CDKN1A was the most altered gene with an increased expression of 11.74 folds in erufosine treated MDA-MB-231 cells followed by CDKN3 (-4.97 fold) and CD20 (-4.85 fold).

4.3.2: Expressional Changes Colorectal Cancer Cells

In CRC cells (SW620), 95% (80/84) of cell cycle relevant genes included in the panel were down-regulated, while only 5% (4/84) were up-regulated after exposure with erufosine. Among the genes, SKP2 showed the highest fold change of -2.95 in expression followed by MCM2 (-2.88 folds) and CCNB1 (-2.82 folds).

4.3.3: Expressional Changes in G2/M Phase Related Genes

As mentioned in *Table 2*, there were 19 genes relevant to G2/M phase of cell cycle included in the panel. Significant fold changes were observed in these genes in the two cell lines (MDA-MB-231 and SW620). Three most altered genes in erufosine treated MDA-MB-231 cells were CDKN3 (-4.97 folds), CCNB1 (-4.15 folds), and CCNA2 (-3.88 folds) as described in *Figure 12*. Likewise, in erufosine treated SW620 cells, the three most altered genes were CCNB1 (-2.82), CDKN3 (-2.63), CCNA2 (-2.36) as described in *Figure 13*.

Figure 12: Fold change in G2/M phase related genes in MDA-MB-231 cells

Figure 13: Fold change in G2/M phase related genes in SW620 cells

4.4. Expressional profiling of G2/M related genes

For above mentioned three most altered genes related to G2/M phase, primers were designed and optimized by amplifying two cDNA samples (untreated SW480 and SW620) in duplicate by conventional PCR methodology (results not shown). Optimized primers were used to identify expressional changes in three G2/M related

genes (CCNA2, CCNB1, CDKN3) via qRT-PCRs in breast (MDA-MB-231, MCF-7) and CRC (SW480, SW620) cells after exposure with low (IC₂₅), medium (IC₅₀) and high (IC₇₅) concentrations of erufosine for 48 hours as shown in *Table 3* related to sample distribution.

In a concentration dependant format, the three selected genes were down-regulated in MDA-MB-231 cells, while there was a minimal induction of the genes at low (IC₂₅) and medium (IC₅₀) concentrations followed by marked inhibition at higher concentrations of erufosine (IC₇₅) in MCF-7 cells (*Figure 14*).

Figure 14: Expressional changes in G2/M phase related genes in breast cancer cells treated with different inhibitory concentrations of erufosine

In CRC cells (SW480 & SW620) treated with different ICs of erufosine, expressional levels of the three selected G2/M related genes were consistently inhibited. However, this inhibition was not in a concentration dependant format for CCNA2 and CCNB1 genes as shown in *Figure 15*.

Figure 15: Expressional changes in G2/M phase related genes in CRC cells treated with different inhibitory concentrations of erufosine

4.5. Pathway Designing

Online IPA software was used to design a pathway by using the expressional changes in cell cycle relevant 84 genes induced by erufosine exposure in breast cancer (MDA-MB-231) and CRC (SW620) cells. This online analysis uses its core knowledge and the experimental data sets to propose signalling cascades for the observed effects. IPA analysis showed the involvement of various gene families like kinases (ATM,

AURKA, B), phosphatases (CDC25A, C), tumour suppressors (BRCA1), anti-apoptotic genes (BCL2, BIRC5), cyclins (CCNA2, CCNB1, CCNB2, CCND2, CCNF, CCNG2), their target kinases (CDKs), activators (CDC6, MKI67), inhibitors (CDKN1A, 2A, CDKN3, CKS1B), regulators (CDC20, MKI67) and facilitators of the cell cycle (MCM2, 3, 4) at various stages of the signalling networking (**Figure 16**). Furthermore, major up-stream regulators proposed by the analysis for the canonical pathway include inhibitors of cell cycle (CDKN1A), a tumour suppressor (TP53) and the activator of cell cycle (E2F family of transcription factors).

Figure 16: Signalling pathway for erufosine mediated cell cycle arrest in target cells

CHAPTER 5: DISCUSSION

Metastatic breast and colorectal cancers are difficult to treat. Available treatment strategies enable us to achieve a very low five years survival rates in advanced stages of these cancers (<22%) (Shah et al., 2014, Martini et al., 2017). The dilemma demands for novel therapeutic compounds with better efficacy and minimal side effects. In this context, erufosine has emerged as a new synthetic compound with reduced gastrointestinal toxicity and haemolytic activity. Although, the compound was synthesized almost two decades ago, a significant attention has been given to evaluate its potential as an anticancer agent in preclinical settings in last five years. Erufosine is a metabolically stable compound with the potential of intravenous administration and crossing the blood-brain barrier. Multiple pathways have been investigated and proposed as a basis for anticancer effects of erufosine against various cancer cell lines. The key molecular pathways, regulated/altered by erufosine to induce its anticancer effects, include induction of apoptosis through caspases, inhibition of proliferation by targeting AKT/mTOR pathway and cell cycle arrest by altering the key regulatory genes (cyclins/CDKs). More importantly, these effects are tumour cell specific as erufosine affects the vital molecular pathways needed for effective tumour cell proliferation (Ansari et al., 2017, Zaharieva et al., 2014, Yosifov et al., 2007, Dineva et al., 2012).

De-regulated cell cycle is one of the key features of cancer cells where canonical pathways are tuned for fast cellular proliferation (Visconti et al., 2016). Considering this, a number of chemotherapeutic and targeted agents have been introduced as therapeutic drugs to halt the fast cell cycle of tumour cells. ALPs comprise a class which also induce cytostatic effects in target tumour cells by altering the AKT/mTOR machinery and cyclins/CDKs cascades (Ríos-Marco et al., 2017). Like other ALPs,

erufosine was found to induce cell cycle arrest (G2/M phase) in breast and CRC cells. Erufosine was also found to be a highly toxic compound and induces cytotoxic effects at low concentrations (IC₅₀: 5.5-8.2µM) in primary and metastatic breast and CRC cells (24 hours exposure). **Table 6** indicates the IC₅₀ concentrations of erufosine after 24, 48 and 72 hours of the exposure with test compound. Breast cancer cells (MDA-MB-231 and MCF-7) were equally responding after 24 hours of treatment, but primary breast cancer cells (MCF-7) were relatively less responsive with increasing time interval, which is possibly due to negative feedback loop and/or development of resistance mechanisms overtime. In CRC cells, both primary and metastatic cells were equally responsive in all time intervals.

Erufosine induced a significant cell cycle arrest (G2/M phase) in breast and CRC cells. After exposure with erufosine (IC₇₅/48 hours), PI staining and FACS analysis, there were 38% more MDA-MB-231 cells in G2/M phase than untreated controls. In comparison, there were only 13% more MCF-7 cells in G2/M phase of the cell cycle after exposure with erufosine (IC₇₅/48 hours). In CRC cells, after treatment of the cells with erufosine (IC₇₅/48 hours), 12 and 17% more SW480 and SW620 cells were found in G2/M phase respectively as compared to their respective untreated controls. Overall, the observed effects were more pronounced in metastatic breast (MDA-MB-231) and CRC (SW620) cells, which reflect a significant potential of erufosine to halt proliferation of metastatic tumour cells and growth at secondary sites. Reasoning behind more sensitive nature of metastatic cancer cells in contrast to primary cancer cells towards erufosine exposure is a promising area for future investigation.

To investigate the mechanistic basis of these cytostatic effects imposed by erufosine, metastatic breast (MDA-MB-231) and CRC (SW620) cells were exposed with the test compound for IC₇₅/48 hours. Following the total RNA extraction and cDNA synthesis

procedure, ready-made cell cycle panels were used to profile the changes in 84 cell cycle relevant genes imposed by erufosine in these malignant cells. The genes, included in the panels, belongs to major families of cell cycle relevant genes i.e., CDKs, cyclins, facilitators, inhibitors, regulators of cell cycle and transcription factors. The detailed information of these genes is available in *Appendix 3*. Erufosine mediated alterations in these genes are shown in **Figure 8** and **Figure 9**. The results showed more pronounced changes (in terms of fold changes) in breast cancer cells (MDA-MB-231) as compared to CRC cells (SW620). The data is in line with our findings from FACS analysis, where we found more intense cell cycle arrest induced by erufosine in MDA-MB-231 (38%) as compared to SW620 (17%) cells. As the MDA-MB-231 and SW620 cells belong to completely different tissue with discrete cellular features, varied levels of sensitivity towards the test compound was not unexpected.

To assess the potential of erufosine in modulating the cell cycle genes in breast cancer cells with varied molecular feature, MDA-MB-231 (triple negative metastatic cells) and MCF-7 (triple positive, primary cells) were exposed with erufosine. Similarly, two different CRC cell lines (SW480: primary cells, SW620: metastatic cells from lymph nodes) were treated with erufosine. To find out concentration dependant effects of the test compound, above mentioned four cell lines were exposed with various concentrations of the test compound (IC_{25} , IC_{50} , IC_{75}). qRT-PCRs for three most altered G2/M phase related genes (CCNA2, CCNB1 and CDKN3) were performed. By enlarge, erufosine was found to induce concentration dependant effects on the selected three genes in different cancer cell lines (*Figure 14* and *Figure 15*), which in turn indicate its potential to affects the target cells (at gene levels) regardless of their different molecular subtypes or origin. The findings also pinpoint that erufosine

induces its effects in target cells by targeting those components which are common in primary and metastatic cells of a malignancy. Considering this, erufosine can be exploited as therapeutic compound in future against primary as well as metastatic phases of a cancer.

IPA, an online pathway analysis developed by Qiagen, is a powerful online tool which helps to understand the biological context of expression analysis experiments by using the inbuilt core knowledge. Powerful algorithms of this software, when combined with the experimental results, provide advanced analysis capabilities to identify the most significant pathways, potential regulatory networks and causal relationships associated with the experimental data. Erufosine exposure induced significant alterations (≥ 2 fold) in 38% (32/84) and 45% (38/84) genes of the panel in MDA-MB-231 and SW620 cells respectively. The significantly altered genes included various cyclins, CDKs, kinases (ATM, AURKA, B), phosphatases (CDC25A, C), tumour suppressors (BRCA1), anti-apoptotic genes (BCL2, BIRC5), activators (CDC6, MKI67), inhibitors (CDKN1A, 2A, CDKN3, CKS1B), regulators (CDC20, MKI67), facilitators of the cell cycle (MCM2, 3, 4) and transcription factors (CKS2, E2F1). The data revealed ability of erufosine to affect multiple players of the cell cycle in target breast and CRC cells. The pathway analysis also proposed CDKN1A (P21), P53 (a master regulator) and E2F1 (a key transcription factor) the main upstream regulators of the induced effects. In this context, investigating the deeper role of these genes in regulating the erufosine mediated cytostatic effects is required. Furthermore, the pathway revealed inhibition of a cyclin-CDK complex (CDC2/CCNB) and its sequestration to minimize the functional activities of this complex. A well-known function of this complex is to drive the cells from G2/M phase of the cell cycle and entry to G1, the next phase. This indication by the

proposed pathway also support our FACS data where erufosine imposed a major halt in G2/M phase. In summary, IPA provided the complex signalling networking governed by erufosine to induce cytostatic effects in target tumour cell lines and further detailed studies are needed to understand the fine tuning of these cascades.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION

Erufosine induces G2/M phase arrest in primary and metastatic breast and CRC cells. Alterations in multiple cell cycle related genes are imposed by erufosine in the target breast and CRC cells. Based on current study, erufosine seems to be a potential antineoplastic and cytostatic agent. Further *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies are needed to support its evaluation in clinical trials.

CHAPTER 7: LIMITATIONS

Due to budget constraints, erufosine mediated alterations in cell cycle relevant genes were identified by one-time experiment while using the ready-made cell cycle panel and one representative cancer cell line of breast cancer and CRC. Considering this, biological repeats and exploring the effects in other representative cancer cell lines are necessary to validate the current results.

Furthermore, the results of this study indicated the expressional changes in cell cycle related genes at transcriptomic levels only. Evaluation of these changes at protein levels are required to authenticate the present findings.

CHAPTER 8: REFERENCES

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APPENDICES

Appendix 1. Materials used in this study

Serial No.	Materials	Company	Catalogue No.	Purpose
1	RPMI1640	Gibco	21875-034	Cell culture medium
2	FBS		10270-106	Serum supplement
3	2mM L-glutamate		A2916801	Support cell growth and synthesis of proteins and nucleic acid
4	Pen Strep		15140-122	Antibiotics
6	MDA-MB-231	American Type Culture Collection	HTB-26	Metastatic breast cancer cells culture
7	MCF-7		HTB-22	Breast cancer cells culture
8	SW480		CCL-228	Colorectal cancer cells culture
9	SW620		CCL-227	Metastatic colorectal cancer cells culture
10	MTT Solution	Serva	20395.01	MTT Assay
11	Propidium Iodide	Serva	33671.01	DNA staining
12	RNeasy Mini Kit	Qiagen	74104	RNA extraction
13	Maxima Reverse Transcriptase	Thermo Scientific	EP0741	cDNA synthesis
14	DNA marker (50bp)	Fermentas	10416014	Marking DNA size
15	Qiagen RT ² Profiler Panel	Qiagen	PAHA-020Z	Human cell cycle analysis
16	SybrGreen PCR master mix	Thermo Scientific	4301955	Realtime PCR

Appendix 2: Array layout (96-well)

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
A	ABL1	ANAPC2	ATM	ATR	AURKA	AURKB	BCCIP	BCL2	BIRC5	BRCA1	BRCA2	CASP3
B	CCNA2	CCNB1	CCNB2	CCNC	CCND1	CCND2	CCND3	CCNE1	CCNF	CCNG1	CCNG2	CCNH
C	CCNT1	CDC16	CDC20	CDC25A	CDC25C	CDC34	CDC6	CDK1	CDK2	CDK4	CDK5R1	CDK5RAP1
D	CDK6	CDK7	CDK8	CDKN1A	CDKN1B	CDKN2A	CDKN2B	CDKN3	CHEK1	CHEK2	CKS1B	CKS2
E	CUL1	CUL2	CUL3	E2F1	E2F4	GADD45A	GTSE1	HUS1	KNTC1	KPNA2	MAD2L1	MAD2L2
F	MCM2	MCM3	MCM4	MCM5	MDM2	MK167	MNAT1	MRE11A	NBN	RAD1	RAD17	RAD51
G	RAD9A	RB1	RBBP8	RBL1	RBL2	SERTAD1	SKP2	STMN1	TFDP1	TFDP2	TP53	WEE1
H	ACTB	B2M	GAPDH	HRPT1	RPLPO	HGDC	RTC	RTC	RTC	PPC	PPC	PPC

Appendix 3: Gene list: RT² Profiler PCR Array

Position	Symbol	Description
A01	ABL1	C-abl oncogene 1, non-receptor tyrosine kinase
A02	ANAPC2	Anaphase promoting complex subunit 2
A03	ATM	Ataxia telangiectasia mutated
A04	ATR	Ataxia telangiectasia and Rad3 related
A05	AURKA	Aurora kinase A
A06	AURKB	Aurora kinase B
A07	BCCIP	BRCA2 and CDKN1A interacting protein
A08	BCL2	B-cell CLL/lymphoma 2
A09	BIRC5	Baculoviral IAP repeat containing 5
A10	BRCA1	Breast cancer 1, early onset
A11	BRCA2	Breast cancer 2, early onset
A12	CASP3	Caspase 3, apoptosis-related cysteine peptidase
B01	CCNA2	Cyclin A2
B02	CCNB1	Cyclin B1
B03	CCNB2	Cyclin B2
B04	CCNC	Cyclin C
B05	CCND1	Cyclin D1
B06	CCND2	Cyclin D2
B07	CCND3	Cyclin D3
B08	CCNE1	Cyclin E1
B09	CCNF	Cyclin F
B10	CCNG1	Cyclin G1
B11	CCNG2	Cyclin G2

B12	CCNH	Cyclin H
C01	CCNT1	Cyclin T1
C02	CDC16	Cell division cycle 16 homolog (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)
C03	CDC20	Cell division cycle 20 homolog (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)
C04	CDC25A	Cell division cycle 25 homolog A (<i>S. pombe</i>)
C05	CDC25C	Cell division cycle 25 homolog C (<i>S. pombe</i>)
C06	CDC34	Cell division cycle 34 homolog (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)
C07	CDC6	Cell division cycle 6 homolog (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)
C08	CDK1	Cyclin-dependent kinase 1
C09	CDK2	Cyclin-dependent kinase 2
C10	CDK4	Cyclin-dependent kinase 4
C11	CDK5R1	Cyclin-dependent kinase 5, regulatory subunit 1 (p35)
C12	CDK5RAP1	CDK5 regulatory subunit associated protein 1
D01	CDK6	Cyclin-dependent kinase 6
D02	CDK7	Cyclin-dependent kinase 7
D03	CDK8	Cyclin-dependent kinase 8
D04	CDKN1A	Cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 1A (p21, Cip1)
D05	CDKN1B	Cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 1B (p27, Kip1)
D06	CDKN2A	Cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 2A (melanoma, p16, inhibits CDK4)
D07	CDKN2B	Cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 2B (p15, inhibits CDK4)
D08	CDKN3	Cyclin-dependent kinase inhibitor 3
D09	CHEK1	CHK1 checkpoint homolog (<i>S. pombe</i>)
D10	CHEK2	CHK2 checkpoint homolog (<i>S. pombe</i>)
D11	CKS1B	CDC28 protein kinase regulatory subunit 1B
D12	CKS2	CDC28 protein kinase regulatory subunit 2
E01	CUL1	Cullin 1
E02	CUL2	Cullin 2
E03	CUL3	Cullin 3
E04	E2F1	E2F transcription factor 1
E05	E2F4	E2F transcription factor 4, p107/p130-binding
E06	GADD45A	Growth arrest and DNA-damage-inducible, alpha
E07	GTSE1	G-2 and S-phase expressed 1
E08	HUS1	HUS1 checkpoint homolog (<i>S. pombe</i>)
E09	KNTC1	Kinetochore associated 1
E10	KPNA2	Karyopherin alpha 2 (RAG cohort 1, importin alpha 1)
E11	MAD2L1	MAD2 mitotic arrest deficient-like 1 (yeast)
E12	MAD2L2	MAD2 mitotic arrest deficient-like 2 (yeast)

F01	MCM2	Minichromosome maintenance complex component 2
F02	MCM3	Minichromosome maintenance complex component 3
F03	MCM4	Minichromosome maintenance complex component 4
F04	MCM5	Minichromosome maintenance complex component 5
F05	MDM2	Mdm2 p53 binding protein homolog (mouse)
F06	MKI67	Antigen identified by monoclonal antibody Ki-67
F07	MNAT1	Menage a trois homolog 1, cyclin H assembly factor (<i>Xenopus laevis</i>)
F08	MRE11A	MRE11 meiotic recombination 11 homolog A (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)
F09	NBN	Nibrin
F10	RAD1	RAD1 homolog (<i>S. pombe</i>)
F11	RAD17	RAD17 homolog (<i>S. pombe</i>)
F12	RAD51	RAD51 homolog (<i>S. cerevisiae</i>)
G01	RAD9A	RAD9 homolog A (<i>S. pombe</i>)
G02	RB1	Retinoblastoma 1
G03	RBBP8	Retinoblastoma binding protein 8
G04	RBL1	Retinoblastoma-like 1 (p107)
G05	RBL2	Retinoblastoma-like 2 (p130)
G06	SERTAD1	SERTA domain containing 1
G07	SKP2	S-phase kinase-associated protein 2 (p45)
G08	STMN1	Stathmin 1
G09	TFDP1	Transcription factor Dp-1
G10	TFDP2	Transcription factor Dp-2 (E2F dimerization partner 2)
G11	TP53	Tumour protein p53
G12	WEE1	WEE1 homolog (<i>S. pombe</i>)
H01	ACTB	Actin, beta
H02	B2M	Beta-2-microglobulin
H03	GAPDH	Glyceraldehyde-3-phosphate dehydrogenase
H04	HPRT1	Hypoxanthine phosphoribosyl transferase 1
H05	RPLP0	Ribosomal protein, large, P0
H06	HGDC	Human Genomic DNA Contamination
H07	RTC	Reverse Transcription Control
H08	RTC	Reverse Transcription Control
H09	RTC	Reverse Transcription Control
H10	PPC	Positive PCR Control
H11	PPC	Positive PCR Control
H12	PPC	Positive PCR Control